

Factors influencing household food waste behaviour

The Challenge

Over 50 % of EU food waste occurs in household. While recent sociological research has highlighted how food waste is simply a consequence of everyday life and the constraints faced by modern households, other research suggests that there is a number of inter-related behaviour, over which households have control that are associated with lower levels of food waste. More evidence is required to understand the antecedents of this behaviour and therefore how it might be changed. This research focuses on the factors influencing some of this behaviour, and furthermore, on the influence this behaviour has on the amount of household food waste.

Policy Implication

Our findings indicate that the main impact on household food waste is from throwing away food which is past the date on packaging. This is in line with findings of other studies which have contributed to the current policy debate on providing new guidance on the application of date labels including a flexible implementation of the date of minimum durability while keeping with food safety rules.

Research

To understand the influence of various factors on food waste behaviours and the stated household food waste, we have developed a conceptual model intended to describe part of the household reasoning process that supports food waste generation. We use structural equation modelling and data extracted for Scottish households from eight waves of the Love Food Hate Waste Household Tracker Survey data from Autumn 2012 through to Spring 2016 (WRAP, 2016).

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Results

Our results suggest that food waste related behaviour influence the level of household food waste, however their influence is contingent on a number of other factors such as socio-demographic characteristics, exposure to information about food waste and the potential savings related to reducing it, and food shopping and meal planning habits. Our models explain between two and three fifths of the variance in food waste, which suggests that additional factors with a potential influence on food waste related behaviour (such as aspects of food safety and risk perceptions) should be included in future similar analyses.

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About

The Land Economy, Environment and Society (LEES) Research Group is one of the largest groupings of economists and social scientists working in the rural, agricultural and land based sectors in the UK. Our vision is to be recognised as one of the leading centres for agricultural and wider rural economic and social research globally, benefiting the land use sector, the environment and rural communities.

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